

Key Sensory Modalities for Adaptive Locomotion in Bio-Inspired Plastic Neural Networks

Pavaris Asawakijtanant¹, Pitiwut Teerakittikul¹, Bawornsak Sakulkueakulsuk¹,
Worasuchad Haomachai^{2*}, and Poramate Manoonpong^{2*}

¹Institute of Field Robotics, King Mongkut’s University of Technology Thonburi, Bangkok, Thailand

²Bio-inspired Robotics & Neural Engineering Lab, School of Information Science & Technology, Vidyasirimedhi Institute of Science & Technology, Rayong, Thailand.

*Corresponding authors: worasuchadh_pro@vistec.ac.th, poramate.m@vistec.ac.th

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Abstract

Reinforcement learning (RL) uses various sensory inputs to learn interactions between the environment and a robotic agent by optimizing high-dimensional neural network policies that maximize reward. However, high-dimensional state spaces introduce several challenges, including difficulty in selecting appropriate sensors and, especially, larger sim-to-real gaps caused by states that are unattainable in the real world. To address these challenges, recent studies aim to use only key sensory inputs and also to bridge the gap between simulation and the real world.

In a recent study [1], a systematic saliency analysis is used to quantify and rank the importance of individual sensory feedback states for locomotion policies. Specifically, integrated gradients computed via backpropagation are used to measure each input dimension’s contribution to the policy output, enabling the identification of a minimal set of essential feedback states. Policies retrained using only these key states can achieve locomotion performance comparable to using the full observation set, demonstrating that unnecessary states can be removed without sacrificing task success. However, although this approach reduces the observation space, sim-to-real transfer of gradient-based RL policies still commonly relies on domain randomization to mitigate modeling errors and sensor mismatch, which are often treated as out-of-distribution (OOD) conditions.

On the other hand, recent work on bio-inspired plastic neural networks [2], optimized with a gradient-free approach, has shown that synaptic plasticity enables online adaptation by adjusting synaptic strengths based on neuronal activity (e.g., Hebbian plasticity). This plasticity mechanism enables legged robots to generalize to out-of-distribution (OOD) conditions and achieve zero-shot sim-to-real transfer without domain randomization. However, current gradient-free plastic neural network

approaches still rely on high-dimensional sensory inputs, and to the best of our knowledge, none has explicitly identified which sensory inputs are essential for legged robot locomotion.

From this point of view, identifying key sensory inputs in plastic neural networks employing gradient-free optimization, while maintaining adaptive locomotion performance under sim-to-real-like OOD conditions, remains challenging. Therefore, in this work, we explored methods to identify the key sensory using an ablation study and evaluating in four conditions of OOD, including (i) slope terrain with inclinations of $\pm 10^\circ$, (ii) mass disturbance, applying additional mass to the robot’s body, (iii) wave terrain, and (iv) morphological changes.

Figure 1: (a) Illustration of the sensory identification procedure. First, we trained locomotion policies using a full sensor suite on flat terrain without domain randomization. Then, we ablated specific sensors before retraining in the same environment. Finally, the key sensors for traversing flat terrain were tested in out-of-distribution (OOD) environments. Scores were used to rank the key sensors, calculated based on the robot’s performance in these OOD environments. (b) Box plots showing performance (maximum distance traveled) across different sensory configurations, evaluated using five policies and 30 rollouts per modality under unseen conditions, including a 10° slope, an additional 1 kg mass attached to the robot body, rough terrain, and morphological changes. Sensor modalities are denoted as: pos (joint position), vel (joint velocity), act (network feedback), IMU (inertial measurement unit data), and FC (foot contact). (c) Learning curves of policies trained without IMU data. One trial fails to learn locomotion, while the other successfully converges. (d) Bar chart illustrating the average performance scores across all OOD environments.

Our experiments are conducted in the Isaac simulation environment using a 19-DoF gecko-like robot, with 4 DoFs per leg and 3 DoFs for the body joints. The robot is equipped with full sensor modality, including five types of sensory feedback: (i) joint positions, (ii) joint velocities, (iii) network feedback,

(iv) IMU data (roll, pitch, and yaw), and (v) foot contact status (boolean). These inputs are fed into a Hebbian network, which is trained to maximize a reward function by optimizing Hebbian learning rules using Evolutionary Strategies (ES). The overview of the simulation training and sensory identification procedure is shown in Figure 1a.

In the first experiment, we trained policies using different sensor modality combinations on flat terrain. For each configuration, three trials with different random seeds were conducted to identify the key sensory inputs required to achieve locomotion before testing under out-of-distribution (OOD) conditions. A policy was considered successful if it consistently learned to achieve locomotion across all three trials. Success was determined based on the reward and linear velocity, with successful policies typically reaching reward values of approximately 60 and a linear velocity of around 0.3 m/s. In contrast, for an unsuccessful policy, as shown in Figures 1c, training policy without the IMU does not achieve sufficient reward and velocity across all trials (i.e., one trial fails). From these experimental results, we obtain ten successful policies with different sensor-modality combinations, which are used in the next experiment to identify the key sensory inputs for handling OOD conditions.

In the second experiment, we aim to identify the key sensory inputs that enable adaptation under four out-of-distribution (OOD) conditions. We use the candidate policies from the previous experiment that successfully learned locomotion on flat terrain and evaluate them on the four OOD conditions, as shown in Figure 1a. We then collect performance metrics (maximum traversal distance) for all candidate policies before scoring them. The most effective sensor-modality combinations for adaptation under OOD conditions are identified as the top three with the highest mean scores in Figure 1d. The highest score is achieved by the full sensor configuration, with a mean score of 8.905. The second highest score (8.862) corresponds to the configuration using joint position, joint velocity, and network feedback, followed by joint position, action, and foot contact with a score of 8.785. As there is no significant performance difference among these top three configurations, we select the policy with the smallest state dimension to reduce the number of observations and mitigate the curse of dimensionality. Consequently, the chosen policy uses joint position, network feedback, and foot contact (boolean) as its sensory inputs to enable adaptation across the four aforementioned OOD cases. Notably, as shown in Figure 1c, policies that lack IMU data are unable to fully learn the locomotion task. However, in the final analysis, IMU data was not selected as a key sensory input. This is because, although certain sensors may dominate the effect of others, removing the IMU and utilizing foot contact can lead to the best performance in this context.

In conclusion, our results show that gradient-free plastic neural network policies can maintain adaptive locomotion under sim-to-real-like OOD conditions using only a compact set of key sensory inputs, with performance comparable to the full-sensor policy. This eases sensor selection and reduces dependence on high-dimensional observations that may be difficult to obtain on real robots, potentially narrowing the sim-to-real gap. Furthermore, this study illustrates that interactions among sensory inputs can steer the learning process in an unfavorable direction, making it difficult for the agent to successfully complete the task. It also presents the challenge of identifying sensor correlations, could be a critical factor in optimizing the performance of adaptive locomotion systems, which is beyond the scope of this study. In future work, we will investigate correlations between sensory inputs and robot behavior by analyzing the dynamic weights of the Hebbian network, and we will evaluate the approach on a real robot.

References

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